

1. Females of parasitoid species *Cardiochiles philippinensis* (left) and *Macrocentrus philippinensis* (right).

Development of *Cardiochiles philippinensis* and *Macrocentrus philippinensis* feeding on 3d-instar larvae of *C. medinalis* under laboratory conditions.

Developmental stage	<i>C. philippinensis</i>		<i>M. philippinensis</i>	
	No.	Duration ^a	No.	Duration ^a
Egg - larva	16	9.5 ± 2.7	14	11.2 ± 2.4
Pupa	16	7.2 ± 1.7	14	6.6 ± 1.2
Adult	10	5.9 ± 0.3	10	11.5 ± 1.8
Total		22.7 ± 3.8		29.4 ± 3.2

^aExpressed in mean days with standard error at 95% confidence.

2. Daily parasitization by *Macrocentrus philippinensis* (MP) and *Cardiochiles philippinensis* (CP) on 3d-instar larvae of *C. medinalis*. Vertical bars show the standard error at 95% confidence.

until pupation. Ten replications for each species were used.

The life cycle of *Cardiochiles philippinensis* feeding on the 3d-instar larvae of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* was 22.7 d; that of *M. philippinensis*, 29.4 d. The difference was due mainly to adult longevity (see table). *Cardiochiles philippinensis* had a shorter adult period, but its reproduction capacity was close to

that of *M. philippinensis*. This implies that *C. philippinensis* may be more efficient.

M. philippinensis had a longer parasitization period than *C. philippinensis* (Fig. 2). Total number of larvae parasitized throughout the lifetime of a female was significantly less for *C. philippinensis* (16.7 ± 0.2) than for *M. philippinensis* (20.1 ± 1.1). ■

Effects of sublethal insecticide application on rice leaffolder (LF)

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Resurgence of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* after insecticide application has been frequently reported. We studied the effects of sublethal levels of three insecticides on the fitness of surviving *C. medinalis*. Insect fitness was taken as survival, development, and reproduction rate.

Fourth-instar larvae were treated on the dorsum region with 0.4 µl of sublethal insecticide solution, using the Arnold Microapplicator. LD₁₀ and LD₄₀ of diazinon and BPMC, and LD₁₅ and LD₃₀ of cypermethrin were used.

Treated larvae were transferred to 40- to 50-d-old IR36 plants and kept to pupation. Emerging moths were sexed and caged in pairs with 40- to 50-d-old plants. Eggs were collected and second-generation larvae from each treatment transferred to 40- to 50-d-old IR36 plants. Larval survival, pupal weights, pupation rate, pupal period, adult longevity, oviposition, and second-generation development were recorded.

Larval development and survival were significantly affected by exposure to sublethal levels of cypermethrin and diazinon. Pupal and adult developmental periods and pupal weights, however, were not affected (see figure).

Effect of exposure to sublethal levels of insecticides on *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* development, growth, and reproduction. Mean \pm SE at 95% confidence.

Cypermethrin had the most effect on pupation and larval survival; pupal survival was not affected, nor was average number of eggs laid per female survivor.

Females from treated larvae appeared normal and oviposition was not affected.

An increase in LF fitness from sublethal doses, therefore, does not account for

insecticide-induced resurgences. Destruction of natural enemies by the insecticides and high recruitment of adults could be possible causes. ■

Integrated pest management – weeds

Agronomic and economic evaluation of herbicides in transplanted rice

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Labor constraints can make timely weeding of a transplanted rice crop difficult in southeastern Rajasthan. In 1989 wet season, I studied five herbicides, farmer's method of weeding 20 and 40 d after transplanting (DT), and an unweeded control. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. All herbicides were applied 7 DT on test variety Jaya.

The weed population was 70% grasses, 25% sedges, and 5% broadleaved weeds. Dominant weeds were *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colona*, *Cyperus difformis*, *C. iria*, *Commelina benghalensis*, and *Eclipta prostrata*.

Effect of weed control method on yield and returns to transplanted rice. Kota, India, 1989.

Treatment ^a	Level (kg/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weed ^a dry weight at harvest (g/m ²)	Net return (\$/ha) over unweeded control	Cost (\$/ha) of weed control	Benefit cost ratio ^b
Anilofos (EC)	0.4	286	4.9	100	112.5	14.6	7.7
Anilofos (EC)	0.6	290	5.1	92	150.0	20.6	7.3
Oxadiazon (EC)	0.4	290	5.2	92	168.8	16.4	10.3
Thiobencarb (G)	1.0	294	5.3	57	187.5	22.8	8.2
Pretilachlor (EC)	0.75	281	4.9	103	112.5	12.2	9.2
Pretilachlor (EC)	1.25	306	5.5	21	225.0	18.5	12.2
Pyrazo sulfuron-ethyl (WP)	0.005	284	5.2	78	168.8	—	—
Pyrazo sulfuron-ethyl (WP)	0.010	279	5.2	83	168.8	—	—
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DT	—	299	5.4	23	206.3	55.2	3.7
Unweeded control	—	201	4.3	206	—	—	—
LSD (0.05)	—	11	0.7	4	—	—	—

^aEC = emulsifiable concentrate, G = granules, WP = wettable powder. Cost: anilofos 30 EC = \$8.9/liter, oxadiazon 25 EC = \$8.5/liter, thiobencarb 10 G = \$2/kg, pretilachlor 50 EC = \$6.3/liter, pyrazo sulfuron-ethyl, not available. Labor required for 2 weedings (20 + 20 DT) and herbicide application (2) in man-days/ha and labor charges = \$1.38/d. ^b Grain price = \$187.5/t.

Rice grain yield was highest (5.5 t/ha) with pretilachlor at 1.25 kg ai/ha (see table). This treatment produced significantly more panicles (306/m²) than other herbicide treatments.

Pretilachlor at 1.25 kg ai/ha had lowest weed dry matter (21 g/m²) and controlled weeds most effectively. Farmer's hand weeding had the lowest benefit:cost ratio; pretilachlor at 1.25 kg ai/ha, the highest. ■